

“Structured Strategic Brand Management Model” in Conceptual & Idealistic Recent Trends

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Abstract

A Strategic Brand management is consciously providing a product with an identity that is understood on all levels. It means both internally and externally and includes customers, employees, suppliers, and vendors. Understanding the niche in which the product resides gives it a relevant differentiated benefit. This translates into the purchase of that product over that of a competitor. Good branding begins with knowing what makes the product special and exploiting its advantages. Strategic management is a field that deals with the major intended and emergent initiatives taken by general managers on behalf of owners, involving utilization of resources, to enhance the performance of firms in their external environments. It entails specifying the organization's mission, vision and objectives, developing policies and plans, often in terms of projects and programs, which are designed to achieve these objectives, and then allocating resources to implement the policies and plans, projects and programs. A balanced scorecard is often used to evaluate the overall performance of the business and its progress towards objectives. This research paper focuses on conceptual and idealistic recent trends in strategic brand management.

Strategic Brand Management

A Brand management is consciously providing a product with an identity that is understood on all levels. It means both internally and externally and includes customers, employees, suppliers, and vendors. Understanding the niche in which the product resides gives it a relevant differentiated benefit. This translates into the purchase of that product over that of a competitor. Good branding begins with knowing what makes the product special and exploiting its advantages. Brand management begins with having a thorough knowledge of the term “brand”. It includes developing a promise, making that promise and maintaining it. It means defining the brand, positioning the brand, and delivering the brand. Brand

management is nothing but an art of creating and sustaining the brand. Branding makes customers committed to your business. A strong brand differentiates your products from the competitors. It gives a quality image to your business.

Brand management includes managing the tangible and intangible characteristics of brand. In case of product brands, the tangibles include the product itself, price, packaging, etc. While in case of service brands, the tangibles include the customers' experience. The intangibles include emotional connections with the product and service. Branding is assembling of various marketing mix medium into a whole so as to give you an identity. It is nothing but capturing your customers mind with your brand name. It gives an image of an experienced, huge and reliable business.

Branding may be for a specific product or could cover an entire corporate image. Brand management is the philosophy and core behind all business development. The rallying cry defines and makes for both an internal and external image. Constantly refining the rallying cry is part of brand management. Branding is the arena that puts the "big picture" perspective into focus and determines where the company takes and makes its future. Strategic management is a field that deals with the major intended and emergent initiatives taken by general managers on behalf of owners, involving utilization of resources, to enhance the performance of firms in their external environments.

It entails specifying the organization's mission, vision and objectives, developing policies and plans, often in terms of projects and programs, which are designed to achieve these objectives, and then allocating resources to implement the policies and plans, projects and programs. A balanced scorecard is often used to evaluate the overall performance of the business and its progress towards objectives. Recent studies and leading management theorists have advocated that strategy needs to start with stakeholders expectations and use a modified balanced scorecard which includes all stakeholders. Strategic management is a level of managerial activity under setting goals and over Tactics.

Strategic management provides overall direction to the enterprise and is closely related to the field of Organization Studies. In the field of business administration it is useful to talk about "strategic alignment" between the organization and its environment or "strategic consistency." Strategic management includes not only the management team but can also include the Board of Directors and other stakeholders of the organization. It depends on the organizational structure.

Characteristics of a Good Brand Name

- Unique and Distinctive
- Extendable
- Easy to pronounce, identified and memorized
- An idea about product's qualities and benefits
- Easily convertible into foreign languages.
- Capable of legal protection and registration.
- Indicate concrete qualities

Another step is to build a brand that maintains loyalty with its customer base and has a strong customer service department. For, having such a department in today's world where one is both experienced and knowledgeable when it comes to helping others can be a rare find. So, companies who represent oneself have having strong customer base and even stronger customer service departments are often more successful than those who do not.

One of the important steps in marketing a brand is to identify the target audience before creating the logo and lettering in relation to marketing. This is because different age groups react differently to a variety of logo and lettering especially as so much is misrepresented by a variety of gangs and others using such material inappropriately. Therefore, if one can define the brand name, logo and lettering and present same to a marketing research review panel or the like, one may be able to gain a better understanding of which audience one needs to direct their product or service to in order to create the most sales. Still, if one can communicate the use of their product or service clearly, establish trust within the community, be that locally or globally, aim marketing at the right audience, build a base of buyers and customer loyalty and offer great customer service, then one is on their way to not only creating and advertising an excellent brand but selling one as well.

Therefore, when looking for steps in building a brand, there are many steps which one can complete to help make the creation of such brand an easier task. These include, knowing your audience, building your brand, finding a great logo and lettering to represent same, targeting the appropriate audience and placing a number of ads in as many online and offline advertising venues one can find. For, after doing so, one may just find that they are selling even more products and services than one had ever dreamed possible. Many organizations that display a dynamic brand name see branding as a subset of marketing management. This is demonstrated by an organizational design that puts the customer at the center of the business. Those organizations recognize that marketing is the name of the game: If you don't sell, you aren't in business. Unfortunately this by no means describes all organizations. For sure, marketing has made progress in boardrooms lately. The competitive pressure and the fast-changing environment of the last decade or so have pushed many more organizations to be in tune with their market. Although those skeptics would be

interested in increasing sales and profitability durably, they resist the idea that the marketing function can help them reach that objective. In fact, they may confuse long- and short-term planning. Coca-Cola's customers would surely shy away from Coke, and would perhaps take to the street altogether, if the taste of the iconic soda changed daily from bitter to sweet. Building trust in a brand therefore requires consistency over a long period of time. It is the task of strategic marketing. When a Kmart department store launches a promotional event, the chances are that Wal-Mart's market intelligence will pick it up immediately and counter it if necessary. Thus, the quick reaction time of Wal-Mart builds sales, as it can annihilate its competitors' price advantage in almost any region. This is a short-term plan, and it is the job of operational marketing.

Process of Renowned Brand Name-

Strong brands reduce customers' perceived monetary, social and safety risks in buying goods/services. The customers can better imagine the intangible goods with the help of brand name. Strong brand organizations have a high market share. The brand should be given good support so that it can sustain itself in long run. It is essential to manage all brands and build brand equity over a period of time. Here comes importance and usefulness of brand management.

Brand management helps in building a corporate image. A brand manager has to oversee overall brand performance. A successful brand can only be created if the brand management system is competent. Strategic management process has following four steps

- Environmental Scanning- Environmental scanning refers to a process of collecting, scrutinizing and providing information for strategic purposes. It helps in analyzing the internal and external factors influencing an organization. After executing the environmental analysis process, management should evaluate it on a continuous basis and strive to improve it.
- Strategy Formulation- Strategy formulation is the process of deciding best course of action for accomplishing organizational objectives and hence achieving organizational purpose. After conducting environment scanning, managers formulate corporate, business and functional strategies.
- Strategy Implementation- Strategy implementation implies making the strategy work as intended or putting the organization's chosen strategy into action. Strategy implementation includes designing the organization's structure, distributing resources, developing decision making process, and managing human resources.
- Strategy Evaluation- Strategy evaluation is the final step of strategy management process. The key strategy evaluation activities are: appraising internal and external factors that are the root of present strategies, measuring performance, and taking remedial / corrective actions. Evaluation

makes sure that the organizational strategy as well as its implementation meets the organizational objectives.

Strategic management is an ongoing process. Therefore, it must be realized that each component interacts with the other components and that this interaction often happens in chorus.

Components of Strategic Management Process

Some of the other steps are as follows:-

- ❖ Objectives of branding - These are descriptive, suggestive, compound, classical, arbitrary and fanciful. It is essential to recognize the role of brand within the corporate branding strategy and the relation of brand to other brand and products.
- ❖ Generation of multiple names - Any potential source of names can be used; organization, management and employees, current or potential customers, agencies and professional consultants.
- ❖ Screening of names on the basis of branding objectives and marketing considerations - The brand names must not have connotations, should be easily pronounceable, should meet the legal requirements etc.
- ❖ Extensive details on each of the finalized names - There should be extensive international legal search done. These searches are at times done on a sequential basis because of the expense involved.
- ❖ Conducting consumer research - Consumer research is often conducted so as to confirm management expectations as to the remembrance and meaningfulness of the brand names. The features of the product, its price and promotion may be shown to the consumers so that they understand the purpose of the brand name and the manner in which it will be used.

On the basis of the above steps, management can finalize the brand name that maximizes the organization's branding and marketing objectives and then formally register the brand name. These components are steps that are carried, in chronological order, when creating a new strategic management plan. Present businesses that have already created a strategic management plan will revert to these steps as per the situation's requirement, so as to make essential changes.

Some concepts of strategic management-

Strategic management can depend upon the size of an organization, and the proclivity to change of its business environment. These points are explained as follows-

- A Global or transnational organization may employ a more structured strategic management model, due to its size, scope of operations, and need to encompass stakeholder views and requirements.
- An SME (Small and Medium Enterprise) may employ an entrepreneurial approach. This is due to its comparatively smaller size and scope of operations, as well as possessing fewer resources.
- An SME's CEO (or general top management) may simply outline a mission, and pursue all activities under that mission.
- Whittington (2001) highlighted four approaches to strategic management, utilizing different factors that organizations may face. These are the Classical, Processual, Evolutionary and Systemic approaches. Each paradigm is suited to specific environmental factors, of which global firms have faced over the past 4/5 decades.
- Mintzberg has stated there are prescriptive (what should be) and descriptive (what is) schools, in the sense that the prescriptive schools are "one size fits all" approaches designed to work as best practice methods, and the descriptive schools merely describe how corporate strategy is devised in given contexts.

It can be said that there is no overriding strategic managerial method, and that a number of differing variables must be taken into account, relative to how a corporate strategic plan is outlined. It can also be said to be a subjective and highly contextual process.

Strategy formation -

The Classical School of strategic management is the most taught and deployed approach, of which most textbooks on the subject convey. The essential points of the approach are "where are we now?", "where do we want to be?" and "how do we get there?" It thus comprises an environmental analysis, a choice of available options, and determining a path for action and implementation. The initial task in strategic management is typically the compilation and dissemination of a mission statement. Following the devising of a mission statement, a firm would then undertake an environmental scanning within the purview of the statement.

Strategic formation is a combination of three main processes which are as follows:

- Performing a situation analysis, self-evaluation and competitor analysis: both internal and external; both micro-environmental and macro-environmental.

Concurrent with this assessment, objectives are set. These objectives should be parallel to a time-line; some are in the short-term and others on the long-term. This involves crafting vision statements (long term view of a possible future), mission statements (the role that the organization gives itself in society), overall corporate objectives (both financial and strategic), strategic business unit objectives (both financial and strategic), and tactical objectives.

Strategy evaluation -

An environmental scan will highlight all pertinent aspects that affect an organization, whether external or sector/industry-based. Such an occurrence will also uncover areas to capitalize on, in addition to areas in which expansion may be unwise. These options, once identified, have to be vetted and screened by an organization. In addition to ascertaining the suitability, feasibility and acceptability of an option, the actual modes of progress have to be determined. Strategic options may span a number of options, including:

- ❖ Growth-based
- ❖ Consolidation
- ❖ Divestment
- ❖ Harvesting

The exact option depends on the given resources of the firm, in addition to the nature of products' performance in given industries. A generally well-performing organization may seek to harvest (i.e. let a product die a natural death in the market) a product, if via portfolio analysis it was performing poorly comparative to others in the market. Additionally, the exact means of implementing a strategy needs to be considered.

A company may opt for an acquisition (actually buying and absorbing a smaller firm), if it meant speedy entry into a market or lack of time in internal development. A strategic alliance (such as a network, consortium or joint venture) can leverage on mutual skills between companies. Some countries, such as India and China, specifically state that FDI in their countries should be executed via a strategic alliance arrangement.

General approaches -

In general terms, there are two main approaches, which are opposite but complement each other in some ways, to strategic management:

The Industrial Organizational Approach

- ❖ based on economic theory- deals with issues like competitive rivalry, resource allocation, economies of scale
- ❖ assumptions- rationality, self discipline behaviour, profit maximization

The Sociological Approach

- ❖ deals primarily with human interactions
- ❖ assumptions — bounded rationality, satisfying behaviour, profit sub-optimality. An example of a company that currently operates this way is Google. The stakeholder focused approach is an example of this modern approach to strategy.

A Strategic management techniques can be viewed as bottom-up, top-down or collaborative processes. In the bottom-up approach, employees submit proposals to their managers who, in turn, funnel the best ideas further up the organization. This is often accomplished by a capital budgeting process. Proposals are assessed using financial criteria such as return on investment or cost-benefit analysis. Cost underestimation and benefit overestimation are major sources of error.

The proposals that are approved form the substance of a new strategy, all of which is done without a grand strategic design or a strategic architect. The top-down approach is the most common by far. In it, the CEO, possibly with the assistance of a strategic planning team, decides on the overall direction the company should take. Some organizations are starting to experiment with collaborative strategic planning techniques that recognize the emergent nature of strategic decisions.

The Strategic decisions should focus on Outcome, Time remaining, and current Value/priority. The outcome comprises both the desired ending goal and the plan designed to reach that goal. Managing strategically requires paying attention to the time remaining to reach a particular level or goal and adjusting the pace and options accordingly. Value/priority relates to the shifting, relative concept of value-add. Strategic decisions should be based on the understanding that the value-add of whatever you are managing is a constantly changing reference point. An objective that begins with a high level of value-add may change due to influence of internal and external factors.

Strategic management by definition is managing with a heads-up approach to outcome, time and relative value, and actively making course corrections as needed. Simulation strategies are also used by managers in an industry. The purpose of simulation gaming is to prepare managers make well rounded decisions. There are two main focuses of the different simulation games, generalized games and functional games. Generalized games are those that are designed to provide participants with new forms of how to adapt to an unfamiliar environment and make business decisions when in doubt. On the other hand, functional games are designed to make participants more aware of being able to deal with situations that bring about one or more problems that are encountered in a corporate function within an industry.

Strategy Hierarchy -

In most (large) corporations there are several levels of management. Corporate strategy is the highest of these levels in the sense that it is the broadest – applying to all parts of the firm – while also incorporating the longest time horizon. It gives direction to corporate values, corporate culture, corporate goals, and corporate missions. Under this broad corporate strategy there are typically business-level competitive strategies and functional unit strategies.

Corporate strategy refers to the overarching strategy of the diversified firm. Such a corporate strategy answers the questions of "which businesses should we be in?" and "how does being in these businesses create synergy and/or add to the competitive advantage of the corporation as a whole?" Business strategy refers to the aggregated strategies of single business firm or a strategic business unit (SBU) in a diversified corporation. According to Michael Porter, a firm must formulate a business strategy that incorporates either cost leadership, differentiation, or focus to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage and long-term success.

Functional strategies include marketing strategies, new product development strategies, human resource strategies, financial strategies, legal strategies, supply-chain strategies, and information technology management strategies. The emphasis is on short and medium term plans and is limited to the domain of each department's functional responsibility. Each functional department attempts to do its part in meeting overall corporate objectives, and hence to some extent their strategies are derived from broader corporate strategies.

Many companies feel that a functional organizational structure is not an efficient way to organize activities so they have reengineered according to processes or SBUs. A strategic business unit is a semi-autonomous unit that is usually responsible for its own budgeting, new product decisions, hiring decisions, and price setting. An SBU is treated as an internal profit centre by corporate headquarters. A technology strategy, for example, although it is focused on technology as a means of achieving an organization's overall objective(s), may include dimensions that are beyond the scope of a single business unit, engineering organization or IT department.

An additional level of strategy called operational strategy was encouraged by Peter Drucker in his theory of management by objectives (MBO). It is very narrow in focus and deals with day-to-day operational activities such as scheduling criteria. It must operate within a budget but is not at liberty to adjust or create that budget. Operational level strategies are informed by business level strategies which, in turn, are informed by corporate level strategies.

Since the turn of the millennium, some firms have reverted to a simpler strategic structure driven by advances in information technology. It is felt that knowledge management systems should be used to share information and create common goals. Strategic divisions are thought to hamper this process. This notion of strategy has been captured under the rubric of dynamic strategy, popularized by Carpenter and Sanders's textbook.

This work builds on that of Brown and Eisenhart as well as Christensen and portrays firm strategy, both business and corporate, as necessarily embracing ongoing strategic change, and the seamless integration of strategy formulation and implementation. Such change and implementation are usually built into the strategy through the staging and pacing facets.

Strategic management limitations -

Although a sense of direction is important, it can also stifle creativity, especially if it is rigidly enforced. In an uncertain and ambiguous world, fluidity can be more important than a finely tuned strategic compass. When a strategy becomes internalized into a corporate culture, it can lead to group think. It can also cause an organization to define itself too narrowly. An example of this is myopia. Many theories of strategic management tend to undergo only brief periods of popularity. A summary of these theories thus inevitably exhibits survivorship bias.

Many theories tend either to be too narrow in focus to build a complete corporate strategy on, or too general and abstract to be applicable to specific situations. Populism or faddishness can have an impact on a particular theory's life cycle and may see application in inappropriate circumstances. See business philosophies and popular management theories for a more critical view of management theories.

In 2000, Gary Hamel coined the term strategic convergence to explain the limited scope of the strategies being used by rivals in greatly differing circumstances. He lamented that strategies converge more than they should, because the more successful ones are imitated by firms that do not understand that the strategic process involves designing a custom strategy for the specifics of each situation.

Conclusion-

The aim of branding is to convey brand message vividly, create customer loyalty, persuade the buyer for the product, and establish an emotional connectivity with the customers. Branding forms customer perceptions about the product. It should raise customer expectations about the product. The primary aim of branding is to create differentiation. One of the most important steps in selling any product or service is the belief one holds in relation to the item. Therefore, only those who strongly believe in the products and services offered by the company are going to be good at selling same. Otherwise, one may want to work

from an advertising or graphic artist perspective in relation to advertising rather than sales when it comes to time to market same.

It can be said that the short-term of today is the long-term of yesterday. As such, operational marketing must fit into strategic marketing. Operational marketing is concerned with all the tasks popularly called marketing, including advertising, merchandising and promotional events. Strategic marketing is concerned with long-term objectives and planning. Among other things, it covers trend analyses, customer service processes, intelligence gathering processes, product development, and branding. In many successful companies, such as Nike, Dell or Staples, the branding strategy will deeply influence the entire organization, as they seek to touch their customers in the same way at every contact-point.

In addition, those marketing-focused companies build brand equity that is bankable. Indeed, once a brand starts being recognizable, it can have a dollar value in the eye of investors and lenders. As such, it goes to the core of business valuation, a metric that is the livelihood of Wall Street analysts and venture capitalists. We may think that it takes decades to generate brand equity unless you are an Internet business; but the shoemaker Nike, for instance, demonstrated that a top global brand could be built in less than 15 years. As a strategic factor, branding can also contribute to a corporate strategy by erecting entry barriers against competitors. For example, when you think about safe family cars, the chances are that Volvo will jump to mind. Volvo is so entrenched in its position of safe family car, that it would be foolish for any other car maker to challenge the Swedish brand on its turf.

Branding can also help a corporation deliver on its going-concern mission. The strengths of the Harley-Davidson and the Ford Mustang brands both saved those products from disappearing at a time where their American competitors were collapsing. Any business organization has the power to take control of its future and can have an emotional impact on its audience. It requires understanding the role of marketing as being different in the short- and the long-terms, with strategic marketing and operational marketing being two distinct activities.

References

1. Lamb, Robert, Boyden Competitive strategic management, Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall, 1984
2. Johnson, G, Scholes, K, Whittington, R Exploring Corporate Strategy, 8th Edition, FT Prentice Hall, Essex, 2008, ISBN 978-0-273-71192-6
3. Deacon, Amos R. L. Simulation and Gaming a Symposium. New York, 1961. Print.
4. Chandler, Alfred Strategy and Structure: Chapters in the history of industrial enterprise, Doubleday, New York, 1962.
5. Selznick, Philip Leadership in Administration: A Sociological Interpretation, Row, Peterson, Evanston IL. 1957.
6. Ansoff, Igor Corporate Strategy McGraw Hill, New York, 1965.
7. Drucker, Peter The Practice of Management, Harper and Row, New York, 1954.
8. Chaffee, E. "Three models of strategy", Academy of Management Review, vol 10, no. 1, 1985.
9. Buzzell, R. and Gale, B. The PIMS Principles: Linking Strategy to Performance, Free Press, New York, 1987.